

Study of Reading and Behaviors Skills to Students with ADHD in South Peloponnese

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ABSTRACT: This paper deals with the factors of reading and behaviors skills by the teaching of language courses to students with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) in the pandemic period covid-19. Methodologically, in parallel with the bibliographical study, used the pedagogical tool, which is referred to the Targeted Individual Structured and Integrated Program for Students with Special Educational needs (TISIPfSEN), in south region of Peloponnese to 15 boys on average 13,8 years old. The students' reading behavior was recorded in manuscript and electronically protocols via mobile phone according the special education and training (SET). In addition, the views of those involved (19 parents, 28 teachers and 38 adults who work in the five educational care additional study centers) were sought with short questionnaires. The data were analyzed according the fundamental scientific knowledge.

KEYWORDS: TISIPfSEN, ADHD, reading, behaviors skills, pandemic period

1. INTRODUCTION

This study explores the pedagogical treatment of problems in people with neurological disorders [1] and special learning difficulties applying of direct teaching by the cognitive-behavioral, ecological-environmental, psychodynamic and neuro-learning theories. According, the Law 3699, 2018, in Greece for the Special Education and Training (SET) for people with disabilities or special educational needs [2] also focus on its phases and the steps on which the teachers will move and guide their students with Attention deficit hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) emphasizes the reading and the behaviors skills, in the pandemic period, when the schools were closed because there is COVID-19. According the European Declaration on the diagnosis and treatment of adults with ADHD [3] this support is continuous and lifelong, until students master the memory mechanisms of reading, writing and understand texts and structure in paragraphs the written word. They also refer to the creation of an appropriate learning environment, with the creation of a special workplace, in order to reduce the chances of distraction [4]. So, the teaching methodology used the 3 dimensions pedagogical materials with fixed and moving cards in a shoebox, individual dossier with binders and a variety of teaching instruments, with visual conceptual facilitators (VCF) to support the comprehension of texts through differentiated instruction (DI). It was used the pedagogical tool TISIPfSEN (Target Individual Structured and Integrated Program for students with Special Educational Needs) [5] to focus on the process of recruiting and processing information and developing the reading skills and strategies. Within the pandemic period, stopped the gradual inclusion of an increasing range of pupils in mainstream schools who would previously have been in segregated, special settings, which has presented new challenges for teachers and teacher education. The development of inclusive pedagogy has become a significant element of teacher education exercise the reading and behavior skills are a complex and multifaceted process as it involves so many factors as the memory and the different types of intelligence. The long-term research of American Psychiatric Association has been able to develop and establish a generally accepted model to children according the statistical manual of mental disorders as the diagnosis ADHD [6]. Also, the early cerebral palsy in school-reading children examine between others and with a magnetic resonance imaging study [1]. But it is not enough the reference to the teaching of methods and ways of acquiring reading, but to the creation of literate pupils, as people who will project their personal skills through reading practice. The writing, speaking, listening and comprehension skills, the ways of thinking, contribute to the conquest of concepts and the establishment of cognitive shapes [7]. Behavior skills are guide pupils, so that through reading they develop their integration into the social and school context. Their development within it ensures a proper reading environment for

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as many pupils as possible. Also, the multifaceted knowledge about the skills required to cultivate reading, in order to recognize the inter-individual problems that arise during its teaching. The aim of modern pedagogical work is therefore to develop students who, through reading, will not only acquire knowledge on specific subjects, but will understand themselves and create correlations between their personal experiences and social structures. This approach adds new responsibilities and roles for the teachers and enhances pedagogical reflections. However, everything mentioned above is difficult to achieve if the concept of reading is not fully understood. In order to better understand reading function, various scientific fields have artificially divided it into individual aspects. There is a following research question set for the study in the caused COVID-19 and that is:

- Pedagogy [8]: How should reading be taught with schools closed?
- Social Pedagogy [9]: Who reads and how and how well being the students?
- Psychometry [10]: What reading and behaviour abilities does the average student have?
- Cognitive psychology [11]: What cognitive and emotional processes determine reading?
- Neuropsychology [1]: Which brain centers regulate reading skills and how?

Therefore, the study begins from the acceptance that it cannot given the term reading and behavior skills a specific one for the children with ADHD and it will depend on the above aspects on which each scientist focuses. As the pandemic period [12] are eligible to receive individualized services within the mainstream class through differentiated instruction (DI) and by distance teaching with the development of specific modifications of the general education curriculum. In general, the mention the reading and behavior skills refer in the language transformation and lays the foundations for the extension of the language process through which the children with ADHD share the experiences, the learnings, the everyday plans, and they collaborate with them.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to the American Psychiatric Association, Attention Deficit Disorder with or without Hyperactivity (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder of attention and hyperactivity – impulsiveness [6]. In the fifth edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DMS-5, 2013) ADHD is defined as a "neurodevelopmental disorder" and, according to the International Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems and the World Health Organization is referred to as "hyperactive disorder". Symptoms of this kind are maintained in adulthood and can cause several difficulties in the social, academic and professional life of the individual in the long term. ADHD is defined as a neurological (neurologic) condition, neurodevelopmental disorder or mental disorder and as a heterogeneous condition [13]. Also, biological theory through the visualization of brain functions is probably the most widespread and valid of all theories as it promotes the belief that ADHD is the result of dysfunction in brain structures [1]. In addition, there are genetic factors that are confused with the causation of ADHD regarding "deficits" in executive function, such as executive behavioral inhibition. Finally, ADHD has also been linked to a sequence of outbreaks other than the individual, such as pre, during and after pregnancy, psychosocial effects and environmental conditions. Most children with ADHD receive some school services, such as special education services and accommodations.

In the United States, efforts to increase access to psychosocial treatments help close gaps in service, which is important to ensure that the millions of school-aged US children who diagnosed with ADHD have received quality treatment according the laws that govern special services for children with disabilities: a) the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) and b) Section 504 of the Rehabilitation Act of 1973 [14]. Also, a majority of school-aged children and adolescents with ADHD received medication treatment and school supports, whereas fewer received recommended psychosocial and psychopedagogic interventions. The teachers, who helped children manage their ADHD symptoms such as it was a present a challenge for teaching them. It values to referred that most children with ADHD are not enrolled in special education classes, but do need extra assistance on a daily basis [15]. At least one in five students with ADHD do not receive school services despite experiencing significant academic and social impairment, a gap that is particularly evident for adolescents and youth from non-English-speaking and/or lower income families. The parent-reported data were obtained for 2,495 children with ADHD aged 4 to 17 years from the National Survey of the Diagnosis and Treatment of ADHD and Tourette Syndrome (NS-DATA) showed that the majority (69.3%) of students with ADHD currently receive one or more school services. The educational support (62.3%) was nearly twice as prevalent as classroom behavior management (32.0%) and more than 3 times as many students with ADHD had an individualized education program (IEP; 42.9%) as a Section 504 plan (13.6%) in the US. In Greece, at least the 2008 [2] the law for the Special education and training for people with disabilities or special educational needs integrated the students with diagnosis ADHD.

The inclusive teaching design for ADHD students according the third phase of Target Individual Structured and Integrated Program for students with Special Educational Needs (TISIPfSEN) encourages a student's positive classroom reading and behaviors skills in the classroom, through a reward system [15]. The classroom teaching management approach a daily relationship step by step and discourages their negative behaviors and has been shown to influence student behavior in a constructive manner, increasing academic engagement. The inclusive teaching design for ADHD use the 'Co-teachers' attitudes for planning and instructional activities for students with disabilities [16]. The reading is a complex procedure and is accomplished through abiding the ability of decoding written symbols which are connected while abide to grammar and syntax rules to the understanding. The reading and behaviors skills as a procedure of receiving, process and use the meaning of the word, the sentence or the text that student with

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ADHD listens or reads [17]. Referring to the ability of decoding, is a crucial skill for the inexperienced or weak readers since they could enter and study a decodable text.

Figure 1 Inclusive teaching design for ADHD students: reading and behaviors skills

So, the purpose of this study is to discuss the factors of reading and behaviors skills to students with ADHD in South Peloponnese in the pandemic period, when the schools were closed because there is COVID-19. Two questions were posed in the working cases. The first examined the observation data on students with ADHD and how they were used in the definition of teaching priorities within the school curriculum. The second also examined the intervention data and the special educational services provided by teachers, parents and professionals in special education centers outside the school curriculum. As with other countries around the world, Greece has faced two main challenges in its response to the coronavirus pandemic with the delivering distance education and managing the examinations. Other challenges have also appeared, which show that Distance education as a challenge and an opportunity. In some parts of the country, school closures began as early as March 5, to protect students from the infection. The Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs has responded to the crisis calling it an opportunity to bring forward long-awaited reforms for the development of the education community's digital skills.

3. METHODOLOGY

To fulfill the objectives of the research focuses on the teaching reading and behavioral subjects to students with Attention Deficit Disorder – Hyperactivity (ADHD). The methodology of this study is mixed as it is made of quality and quantity data and always requires a series of systematic steps to be followed. After conceptualize the research, setting objectives, the literature review, the study area has been done in South Peloponnese. The qualitative data of the research was present here and it was extracted from the target group fifteen (15) boy's student case studies with average 13,8 years old with ADHD's evidences, and who is preoccupied to the core of the observations and interventions methodology. The quantitative data was collected through a questionnaire, which was completed by 38 adults who work in the five educational care additional study centers into different cities and they offer help for the instructional objects with average 36 years old. The survey, in this category was collected has data also, from the 19 parents with average 33 years old. Additionally, in this methodology is been consisted by the 28 teachers with average 32 years old who stands by the students with diagnosis ADHD's by using the pedagogical tool TISIPfSEN (Target Individual Structured and Integrated Program for students with Special Educational Needs). The Methodology process and the procedure of extraction of quality research lasted 14 months and was as follows. First of all, the study a bibliography review was made, then the goals were formulated, the research questions were written and then the research tool was designed. Afterwards a pilot research was made, to note possible uncertainties in the formulation of questions and to finalize the questionnaire. For the validity of the structure of the questionnaire a pilot research was done in twenty-eight adults (parents, teachers, adults). The validity pointer of the Cronbach-a questionnaire gave a result of 0.88, for the 30 variables. Before the conduct of the research there was a full update to the participants for the theme and the goal of the research, the procedure and the educational benefit of it. Furthermore, the participation of the children, parents, teachers and other adults in the research was voluntary. The research tools of the quality data from the research of the ADHD students were gathered through the methodology of observation and with the informal pedagogical evaluation. This was done by using the protocols of SET Checklists of basic skills (CBS) of learning readiness and the special education needs according to the Framework Curriculum of Special Education (FCSE) and the Form of the Teaching Interactions (FTI). The lists are designed to examine either the presence or not of specific characteristics and behaviors. They can be constructed for each field of development, such as communication, sentimental and cognitive skills. Checklists need to be structured by the teachers. Control lists are useful and effective. The use of visual representations for the presentation of data from evaluation activities

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makes their understanding easier. The protocols of CBS of learning readiness contains areas of observation when it comes to Oral language, Psychomotricity Activity, Mental skills and Emotional organization skills. The research tools of the quality data from the research of the ADHD students were gathered through the methodology of observation and with the informal pedagogical evaluation. This was done by using the protocols of SET which recorded with the Checklists of basic skills (CBS) of learning readiness and the special education needs according to the Framework Curriculum of Special Education (FCSE) and the protocols of the Teaching Interactions. The lists are designed to examine either the presence or not of specific characteristics and behaviors of ADHD. They be constructed for each field of development, such as communication, sentimental and cognitive skills. Control Checklists need to be structured by the teachers in tables and are useful and effective. The use of visual lines representations for the presentation of data from evaluation activities makes their understanding easier the other -observations. The protocols of CBS of learning readiness contains areas of observation when it comes to Oral language, Psychomotricity Activity, Mental skills and Emotional organization skills [7]. The completion of CBS tables is done through excel panels as it follows in the horizontal lines, teacher records the skills of every area that are evaluated according to interactive pedagogical relationship and experience of the students' performances in classroom reading and behavior skills. In the vertical lines, teacher exhibits the school semesters regarding the typical and mandatory education counting in ascending order from number (1) which corresponds to the first semester of attending kindergarten up to the (22) th semester of study, corresponding to the third grade of the second semester of the (3th class of Secondary education) Gymnasium. The horizontal compact line that penetrates the horizontal lines, is the "base line" (yellow color) which corresponds to the current semester of the students according to their typical and obligatory education. The second fluctuation line (blue color) shows the average of disturbed or normal performance of the students in each skill during the etero-observations.

The research process requires interdisciplinary collaboration between the students with ADHD and the adults who work in the five educational care additional study centers into different cities Kalamata, Sparta, Tripoli, Argos, Nafpleon. The parents and teachers have participated in the based methodology of observing special educational needs, using the pedagogical tool of TISIPfSEN. Also, based on the multi-sensory support of teaching, with the creation of cognitive machines, with three-dimensional pedagogical material with fixed and mobile cards in binders and a variety of teaching tools, with visual conceptual facilitators, supports textual comprehension.

In order to better implement the research process and the course with differentiated language interventions tailored to the specific educational needs of ADHD, dividing the teaching objective into small teaching steps accompanied by corresponding textual activities so that the student keeps his attention better. Also, the environment of the research process is required to be quiet without sustained stimulation stimuli to avoid distraction. Moreover, the individual work -T (I) SIPfSEN- has organized, controlling the interference from others. In the pandemic period covid-19, the research process utilized the interaction with the computer – meeting with a telecommunication by distance teaching reading and behavior skills.

Table 1. The participants of study

A/N	Data from	Number	Average/ years old
1	students with ADHD	15	13,8
2	adults who work in the five educational care additional study centers into different cities	38	36
3	parents	19	33
4	teachers	28	32
	totals	100	

The Methodology of Observation Data used two pedagogical tools. The first tool TISIPfSEN was the Individual systematic and empirical observations of a students with ADHD. In this the observation methodology is carried out in 15 case studies of students with ADHD. The second tool TISIPfSEN was the Informal pedagogical assessment (IPA) with hetero observations and auto observations.

With the first tool T (I) SIPfSEN emphasized the observation data from the individualities (I) of students. It has used particular protocols according the SET with systematically teaching experience observations and collected data from the individual story, school story, family story and the diagnosis. In the school history, it is recorded through the systematic empirical hetero-observations that the students attend from the 16th semester of the sixth grade of primary (4) boys, from the 17th semester of the first grade of School Junior High School (4 boys), from the 18th semester of the first grade of School Junior High School (4 boys) and from the 19th semester of the second grade of School Junior High School (3 boys), according the formal and compulsory education.

With the second tool TI (S-I-P) FSEN emphasized the observation data from the Structured and Integrated Program. It has used particular tables protocols according the SET to record the performance and the informal pedagogical assessment of specific reading and behavior difficulties. The Informal pedagogical assessment (IPA) is the tool by the second phase of TISIPfSEN, is using the Basic Skills Control Lists (BSCL) to understand the specific reading and behaviors difficulties. Cross-references are recorded as factors involved in the informal pedagogical assessment (IPA), focusing on what the students do with ADHD, emphasizing the concentration and consistency of their work at a certain time.

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The Informal Pedagogical Assessment (IPA) is recording the reading skills level in the various problem areas and behavior skills. Deviations are recorded in the semesters of the class attended and monitored by the weekly timetable. These BSCL include skills from the neuro-developmental areas of learning readiness (1), special educational needs as (2), skills from the cognitive domains defined by the Interdisciplinary Framework of Analytical Curriculum of Special Education and skills of Curriculums in Greek Language Courses on General Learning Difficulties (3) and skills from areas of perception, memory, graphic space, reading, mathematics, behavior, as defined in the Experimental Program of Specific Learning Difficulties (4). Students with ADHD may have evidence of abusive behavior because they have difficulty understanding and following the rules governing the learning environment. The distance teaching with the Internet hetero-observe and recorded with delinquent behavior. It is described with the inability to follow social rules, when they have difficulty creating and maintaining good interpersonal relationships with their peers and teachers.

The Informal pedagogical assessments of reading and behavioral problems (self-observations) refer to the interpersonal relationships the teachers develop with the students with ADHD and the emotions that are born to them by the interactions with the students with ADHD, and they are part of the IPA of the reading and behavioral problems. In this context, the feelings and thoughts regarding the informal pedagogical assessments are recorded from the students' responses to the goals, examining their functionality and correspondence with their abilities and promoting school performances. As regards the self-observations of reading and behavior difficulties in a particular lesson, we examined the interactions developed in shaping relationships, feedback, updating the individualized curriculums, and increasing of the effectiveness of the interventions.

The Methodology of Intervention Data used three others pedagogical tools according the TISIPfSEN [18]. So, the third tool was the particular design emphasizing in the targeted individual teaching differentiated integration interventions in Greek language courses for 15 students with ADHD by are defining in the special pedagogical interventions. The fourth tool was the diversified educational teaching interventions of students with pedagogical materials applications within and outside the school curriculum according the teaching priorities. The fifth tool was the assessment of interventions with particular protocols according the SET in the autonomy skills, in the time of reading and in the express of sentiments for all this teaching situation. Also, the collaboration record with the parents is included in the fifth phase of the TISIPfSEN and the protocols of the teaching intervention. This is the task of reading and understanding the emotional code governing inter-family relationships, as they are displayed by the child in the teacher-student interactions.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

The qualitative data analysis instruments according to the pedagogical tool TISIPfSEN focus to the 15 students with ADHD and limited to SWOT Analysis (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats). Among the advantages included data obtained from other observations in accordance with SET protocols. The weak elements of the study included the difficulties of students to work with properly designed and adapted pedagogical material in the special educational needs of ADHD. Because, the distance learning was virtual and did not create provocative language stimuli with the three-dimensional cognitive machines and the appropriate visual conceptual facilitators. Strengths,

Also, in the opportunities included the data obtained from the hetero- observations in accordance with the protocols of the SET. These gathered as positive responses from the students and their familiarity with the technologies of communication and information technology, utilizing the means such as the laptop, the mobile smart phone but also the tablet. Final, the threats points included the data obtained from the self-observations according to the protocols of the SET. In these, the students were not always satisfied with this way of teaching and need the frequent and constant reminder of the mother to connect to the lesson.

The quantitative data analysis was based on the questionnaire which included 10 questions referring to ADHD descriptions regarding the careless student, the hyperactive, the impulsive and the mixed type of student behavior. This was sent electronically and asked to be answered by distance learning teachers due to the pandemic, and from the parents who assisted with online lessons and facilitated the students when they had difficulty flowing of school schedule. It was also sent electronically to the professionals of the educational study and care centers outside of school hours. These services were paid by the parents after an agreement who they had made with the owners of the centers. Among the professionals there were 15 with postgraduate studies in special education, who had not chosen teaching at school as deputies but preferred to offer services in the city where they lived and themselves and their families.

Table 2. The positive answers from adults.

a/n	The questionnaire	Parents (N=19)	Teachers (N=28)	adults who support them in the five educational care additional study centers into different cities (N=38)
1	He is focused for 3-6 minutes when he reads from his book	10	25	30
2	He is focused when reading the text remotely with the computer	12	15	20
3	Remains in place until the lesson is completed for 20 minutes	10	15	25

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4	He gets up from the position of the beggar to go to the toilet	15	15	30
5	Interrupts the lesson with irrelevant comments from what is being taught	14	20	30
6	Interrupts his teacher when he reads for no reason	10	22	30
7	Raises his hand in the online lesson for no reason	10	20	20
8	Sits with one foot on the chair like a pelican (ready to fly)	12	15	15
9	He shakes his legs in class as if he were "sucking" with the machine	14	14	20
10	He is indifferent and does not look at the lesson on the screen	15	25	30

The initial analysis of the questionnaire shows that more than 50% of the adult respondents answered positively to the 10 questions by their parents, teachers and professionals. Of particular interest are the questions (1), (4), (5), (6), (10) where more than 70% are answered positively by both teachers and professionals.

5. RESULTS

Two questions were posed in the working cases. In the first has examined the observation data on students with ADHD and how they were used in the definition of teaching priorities within the school curriculum. The focus for 3-6 minutes when they read from their book were the main teaching objective of interventions and the steps emphasized to understand the text as in the history lesson. This was differentiated with 20 lines, with emphasis on the phonological type and morphology of the words (20), with 10-15 Visual conceptual facilitators (VCF).

The (T) ISIPFSEN and targeted teaching priorities are tailored to students with ADHD and the differentiated teaching objective (short-term) has collected data for 15 minutes from the read (perceptual reading) in the exercises to understand the text using in behavior the 5-8 visual meaning facilitators VCF. Also, the teachers helped them to apply the grammatical rules, using the personal computer, the mobile phone and the tablet. The reading and behavior exercises for understanding referred in particular difficulties, as also the number and the type of words into the frame of pedagogical materials, activities, of folders with word cards and with the VCF cards. The individuated of reading and behavior exercises for understanding the difficulty in particular number and type of words, the pedagogical materials such as the folder with 3 dimensions containing -activities- with word cards and image cards with VCF were defined for each teaching intervention separately and for each one of student with ADHD. Among the teaching steps used the knowledge mechanisms for reading and behavior skills. First the differentiated pedagogical materials as the folder with fixed and mobile cards, also the shoe box with the differentiated using with a representation of a history battle and the tablet or mobile where they recorded their voice when reading. The exercises were with scaling difficulties and ask from the students od ADHD, step by step to shows the 10 mobile cards out of 20 with certain words or to read 10 cards out of 20 with certain words 10 words of the phonological type from the folder. The differentiated pedagogical material, the teaching steps and timetable of interventions, the exercises with the reading, the reading speed, the understanding, the identifying, the sequence writing with word and image, the expression writing are presented within the Folder Steps. Also, the reading exercises have taught with the particular and programmed individual telecommunications with personal computer and sometimes from the data of mobile phone. The reading and behavior skills are supported with the concentrating of students in about 10 minutes with the exercises of reading,

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linguistic understanding, writing and sequencing. So, when the students with ADHD gather in about 5 minutes in finding the key words in up to 11 lines and 100 words of a certain phonological type, with the help of 5-8 visual conceptual facilitators.

In the second question also has examined the intervention data and the special educational inclusion Services which and were provided by teachers, parents and professionals in special education centers outside the school curriculum. Weaknesses in reading, spelling and comprehension of texts were reflected in the Basic Reading Skills. Children had difficulty distinguishing the meaning of words according to their occupations or distinguishing what part of speech each word is according to its spelling. These records demonstrate that teachers can understand the reading difficulties caused by ADHD dysfunction. The special learning disabilities recorded low levels of hyperactivity and inattention and are sufficient to confirm the two most characteristic symptoms of the disorder. Students are unable to sit still for 15 minutes (see "The positive answers from adults"). "The positive answers from adults". 1. He is focused for 3-6 minutes when he reads from his book and 3. Remains in place until the lesson is completed for 20 minutes), constantly shaking their arms or legs and occupying their arms with any object in front of them (see "The positive answers from adults"). "The positive answers from adults". 8. Sits with one foot on the chair like a pelican (ready to fly), and 9. He shakes his legs in class as if he were "sucking" with the machine). Even children can be described as overly enthusiastic and often, they answer without thinking much and before the teachers finish his question (see "The positive answers from adults"). 5. Interrupts the lesson with irrelevant comments from what is being taught and 6. Interrupts his teacher when he reads for no reason). Additionally, during the lesson, they look around and focus on stimuli unrelated to the lesson. All the above observations are related to the symptoms of ADHD and the dysfunctions it causes. In conclusion, the hypothesis that teachers and the adults who support them, can recognize the symptoms of the disorder in the students is fully documented with the help of the first and the second tool pedagogical TISIPfSEN. Checking the data from the beliefs of parents, adults who support them and teachers, they seem to agree even if at first, they seem a little hesitant, the above data is verified through the following dialogue:

Parent: "In my opinion, a teacher should be constantly informed about general and special education issues. The needs and abilities of children differ. "We may teach certain lessons, but that does not mean that all children understand them in the same way."

Teacher: "Yes, I believe that especially nowadays a philologist should and can aim at lifelong learning. There is an infinite amount of informative material on the internet, in books and even in news TV shows. It is the duty of every teacher to take into account the needs of all children and to take care of the progress of all his students and for each one individually. "

Adult who supports: "I agree with you. In addition, there are so many seminars that one can attend for free or at a low cost. The important thing is to love your job and try to develop it according to the needs of your students. Anyone who has an appetite in our time, with such a wide range of options can find the way. Anyway, I started this discussion for you because in the study department of the sixth grade I observe the learning difficulties that student faces and his behavior in the classroom. Taking into account what I know about ADHD disorder and its symptoms, I recognize some basic symptoms of it in the student. It goes without saying that I have done my research on the symptoms of ADHD both on the internet and in books on special education and special learning difficulties. "

In the above dialogue, the importance of informing everyone about reading and behavioral skills to students with ADHD is highlighted so that they can help all students. One of the adults who supports in private centers welcomes this belief and she also seems to have identified symptoms of the disorder in her students. The owner of the center, at first seems somewhat hesitant and states that the symptoms could be due to some form of dyslexia but she also agrees that a philologist can understand the ADHD disorders and the reading difficulties they cause. She, in turn, shows confidence in the teachers' judgment and wants to support the efforts because she believes that with the right pedagogical tools and the right approach, they will be able to support appropriate reading and behavioral skills to students with ADHD.

6. DISCUSSION

The classroom reading and behaviors skills put the psychosocial [13] and psycho-pedagogic interventions and are discussed them in the frame the school services [11], the school supports [11], the special classes and the special schools [7] which were open in all the pandemic period [12]. The school services participate actively and effectively in understanding the disorder, aiming to offer as much help as they can through the process of learning and social life of the child within the school context. The fact that the teaching goals set for the student were common to the goals of the class of the general school in which he attends played a decisive role in the success of the philologist to realize the disorders arising from ADHD.

The school support to the students with ADHD into the special classes [19] and the special schools, identifies the school life [9] of the student using the targeted pedagogical tools as the TISIPfSEN and appropriate learning practices can detect and intervene the difficulties of ADHD. Every teacher has in his hands several "tools" to use to identify and understand the weaknesses that arise from the disorder and make it difficult for the student to integrate smoothly into the general education department. In particular, the supervision of some initial steps in the learning process of children (for example, spelling in school, the form of written speech, etc.) decisively helps the teacher to acquire basic criteria for pedagogical assessment by the TISIPfSEN. In addition, by recording hetero-observations, it has been shown that educators caring for students with ADHD into special classes and special schools when they can collect considerable and important data on behavior and school performance in reading and understanding texts. With these data

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they can in the second stage, intervene together treating and dealing with the difficulties of reading and behaviors skills the students' disorder.

According to the data, this study draws from the theoretical part of Christakis [8], teachers are not indifferent to reading and behavioral difficulties and understand the importance of reading behaviors as we have noted (see 2. He is focused when reading the text remotely with the computer, 4. He gets up from the position of the beggar to go to the toilet, 7. Raises his hand in the online lesson for no reason, and 10. He is indifferent and does not look at the lesson on the screen). In addition, pedagogical tests by the TISIPfSEN [20] [21] in combination with differential diagnosis and interdisciplinary services help to effectively detect learning needs and provide the opportunity to make the necessary changes according to the developmental abilities of students. The understanding of the dysfunctions in the field of reading and written speech is achieved through the recording of the teaching intervention and the qualitative analysis of the errors. Also, in this present study point the need to the importance of how it will be able to contribute to the field to manage the classroom reading and behaviors skills, by the adaptive psychosocial [10] and psycho-pedagogical interventions by the Target Individual Structured and Integrated Program for students with Special Educational Needs [20] (TISIPfSEN).

7. CONCLUSION

The conclusions are come from the points when the teachers and the adults who support them in the five educational care additional study centers into different cities have gaps in literary lessons and have difficulty concentrating for a certain amount of time. The first conclude point came from all, the students with ADHD, the teachers, the adults and the parents. The reading and behavior skills lined by to help them to obtain the grades to pass the class. The second conclude point came from the students with ADHD, who still have a great difficulty in reading, producing and understanding writing. They are not easy to interact with other children, are closed and shy and their inability to follow rules, their classmates do not want to participate in group games and discussions often. This has the consequence for them of having few friends. At home, they interact with several conflicts between them and with the others members of family, over time [14]. The third conclude point came from the teachers who are often put nonrealistic goals without the self-observations and the pedagogical reflections to set a teaching priority on what happens to the students "here and now". At least fourteen months, in the pandemic period [12] the teaching support at school is considered as an urgent priority for restoring quietness in the school community, without however interfering with the students' attitudes within the schools. So, the teachers also find it difficult to observe themselves and the behavior they develop in interacting with ADHD students.

The methodology of teaching interventions refers to the students with ADHD [14] with emphasis on its de-categorization and decriminalization in order to construct an individualized curriculum that addresses its particular difficulties and needs and takes into account the learning readiness, capabilities and interests. So, the differentiated teaching objectives, differentiated pedagogical materials, and educational tools highlight inventive cognitive machines, which are part of the didactic intervention [15]. The visual conceptual facilitators are defined in texts with specific content, mainly by assessing the child's or young person's experiences with a predetermined number and type of words.

The teaching by of understanding behaviors skills with 3D reading machine in the end, purpose to learn the student with ADHD to self-evaluate his performance and the teaching material by putting the emoji that expresses him (happy, sad and indifferent) [18]. It is noted that the students with ADHD have "bad" school performances, they have also the school failures accumulates and their self-esteem is low and they tend to resign, especially when they cannot solve an exercise immediately. In the classroom, they do not advance to make their exercises while copying from the board and makes several mistakes, as they are lost and confused. So, in this study of reading and behaviors skills to students with ADHD in South Peloponnese [13], when they made too many misspellings, and they had difficulties by the pedagogical tool TISIPfSEN help them organizing their ideas and finding the right words.

8. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. Attention Deficit Disorder – Hyperactivity (ADHD).
2. Framework Curriculum of Special Education (FCSE).
3. Target Individual Structured and Integrated Program for students with Special Educational Needs (TISIPfSEN).
4. Visual conceptual facilitators (VCF).
5. Special Education and Training (SET).
6. Informal pedagogical assessment (IPA).
7. Basic Skills Control Lists (BSCL).
8. Form of the Teaching Interactions (FTI).
9. Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA).
10. Differentiated instruction (DI).
11. Checklists of basic skills (CBS).
12. Individualized education program (IEP).

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